

3D'omics website www.3domics.eu

Deliverable 2.1

Month 3 (November 2021)

Table of contents

General project information	3
Project partners	3
The 3D'omics website	4
Homepage	4
Consortium	5
Positions available	5
Events	6
Future pages	6

General project information

Title	Three-dimensional holo'omic landscapes to unveil host-microbiota interactions shaping animal production
Acronym	3D'omics
Grant Agreement No.	101000309
Funding Programme	Horizon 2020
Instrument	RIA (Research and Innovation Action)
Project start date	01/09/2021
Duration of the project	48 months

Project partners

#	Partner	Abbrev	Type	Country
1	University of Copenhagen	UCPH	University	Denmark
2	Center for Genomic Regulation	CRG	Research Center	Spain
3	Veterinary University of Vienna	UVM	University	Austria
4	Max Delbrück Center	MDC	Research Center	Germany
5	KU Leuven	KUL	University	Belgium
6	ETH Zurich	ETH	University	Switzerland
7	Ben Gurion University	BGU	University	Israel
8	Norwegian University of Life Sciences	NMBU	University	Norway
9	Afekta Technologies Limited	ATL	Industry, SME	Finland
10	Aviagen, Inc.	AVI	Industry	United Kingdom
11	Novogene Netherlands B.V.	NGE	Industry	The Netherlands
12	Biomin, GmbH	BIO	Industry	Austria
13	Norsvin SA	NOR	Industry	Norway

The 3D'omics website

This document details the Project Website for 3D'omics, which is public and created for external communication about and on the project. Internal communication and reporting will be done via a monthly newsletter, e-mail, and Jira (management software). After discussing with all the beneficiaries, we decided not to use the website for internal communication via login to an intranet.

The website domain is hosted by <https://www.one.com/> and it was created and will be maintained by the communications manager using the platform Mobirise. The web address is <https://www.3domics.eu/>.

It is part of Task 2.1, visual communication strategy, led by UCPH, from M1-M48, which will centralise all the visual communication strategy. Social Media channels were also created and will be managed by the communications manager, namely Twitter, Instagram, Youtube and LinkedIn. These, in the form of links through the respective icons, were integrated into the website to ensure information related to 3D'omics reaches all kinds of public stakeholders. In the future, events, videos, articles, etc. related to the project and the team will be broadcasted on social media, as well as mentioned on the website.

Homepage

WHO WE ARE

The H2020 3D'omics project

Three-dimensional holo'omic landscapes to unveil host-microbiota interactions shaping animal production is an exciting multi-disciplinary project across 11 countries.

COME JOIN US ONLINE TO LEARN ABOUT THE PROJECT, MEET THE TEAM AND SEE WHAT EXCITING POSTDOCTORAL POSITIONS WE HAVE COMING UP! Sign up [here](#).

You can find a summary of the project on the European Commission's website [here](#).

NOR ATL
NMBU UCPH
AVI NGE MDC
KUL UVM
ETH BIO
CRG

CRG

CRG

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement number No. 101000309

The homepage is simple, with links to the project social media and the different pages that make up the website. Whenever there is an event or news worth mentioning, these will be highlighted on the homepage, with the respective link to know more. It contains a map with the location of the different partners, that will be replaced with a more professional-looking one once the first explainer video is made (as part of D2.3), as it will contain a map to locate all the beneficiaries and their role in the project. Once the videos are made, they will also be included on the website (as well as YouTube).

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Consortium

3D'omics

Home Consortium Jobs Events Contact Us

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UCPH - Denmark
UVM - Austria
KUL - Belgium
ETH - Switzerland
BGU - Israel
NMBU - Norway

AVI UCPH
NGE MDC
KUL UVM
ETH BIO
CRG
BGU

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Regarding the Consortium, there is a simple general landing page and then a page for each beneficiary, where readers can learn about the institutions, the team, the facilities and the role of each partner in the project. Links to their institutions and labs are also included.

Positions available

3D'omics

Home Consortium Jobs Events Contact Us

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Jobs
MDC
CRG
UCPH

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CRG
BGU

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Whenever we have positions available or coming up in the future to join the 3D'omics team, they will be advertised on the website, with information on the positions and the hiring partners, and links to the official job ad and application when available.

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Events

The screenshot shows the 3D'omics website with a navigation menu (Home, Consortium, Jobs, Events, Contact Us) and a central event announcement. The announcement includes the 3D'omics logo, the event title 'Project presentation online event', an agenda list, the date and time 'November 30th, 2021 14:30-16:00 CET', and a 'Sign up below!' link. Below the announcement is a sign-up form with fields for 'Name' and 'Type your email here', and a 'Join us!' button. A small text block below the form reads: 'Join our online project presentation on 30/Nov, 14:30 Copenhagen time to learn more about the project, meet the team and find out what postdoc positions we have coming up! How we treat personal data.'

Whenever there is an event coming up (either outreach - Task 2.4 Outreach and public engagement activities, led by UCPH-G, from months M1-M48 -, or training activities - Task 2.6 Training activities, led by NMBU, from M25-M48), it will be shared via social media, as well as posted on the website. If it requires signing up, then there will be a sign-up form, accompanied by a link to information on how we treat personal data (that will vary, depending on which partner(s) is/are in charge of the event).

The current event, as of the deadline of the present deliverable, is an online presentation of the project, where there will be an overview of the project, followed by short presentations by a few partners and in the end attendees will have the opportunity to ask questions to the team.

Future pages

This deliverable is due on month 3, which means the project does not have data or publications yet. Therefore, the aim for the first quarter has been to introduce the project and the team.

The next stage will be to engage and produce content aimed at the different stakeholders, from science to industry and the general public. As the project progresses, we will ensure that general knowledge about animal-microorganisms systems, as well as the specific knowledge generated in 3D'omics reaches stakeholders and researchers, but also the general public, including young students.

A blog section will be added soon, with articles about or relating to the project, that will be useful for both introducing the project to a wider audience and later keep the up to date with progress, as well as eventually aid with networking with the various sectors of stakeholders, including other consortia.

When we start to plan events and have dates for them, there will be a project activities

calendar on the website. The agenda will specify the public activities (e.g. training courses, outreach talks) organised by 3D'omics and/or its partners. When any results that can be shared and/or published publicly are available, there will also be a list of publications derived from the project, and other links to external relevant resources.

